

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MAWIRE****FIRST NAME: SIMBARASHE****PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401****COURSE CODE: MDIA****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

WHAT MAKES AN EXCELLENT PAPER?

1) INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest challenges I faced as I started this course is narrowing my thoughts and ideas to focusing only on period one coursepack provided by our institution. Over the years I conducted studies in business management, project management, as well as social sciences; Psychology and Human Development. Transitioning from such broad field areas to this niche area of Master of Science in Diplomacy and International Affairs (MDIA) program has been somewhat challenging, at the same time an exciting process. As I begin my study journey on ACA-401 Period One, I find it to be an information-hub full of guidelines on how to write an academic essay. This essay is a response paper to the information delivered to students in first period. It serves as a reference point of demonstrated ability to follow prescribed guidelines of the shared educational materials, showcasing my understanding of given task. More precisely, demonstrating the ability to write an excellent paper, which is free from grammatical errors, one which follows a given structure, proper punctuations and referencing. What has become apparent to me as I dive into my period one study material is that, Euclid University stands out in many ways, particularly on equipping me with the basic knowledge necessary to develop excellent writing skills. As I highlighted in my opening statements that, I attained a number of academic qualifications from varying tertiary institutions and varying fields of study.

Moving from undergraduate studies, progressing to graduate level degree programs, I wholly testify that never was I ever given a course or paper focused on academic writing at any other institutions at a graduate level. It was always assumed that such skills had already been gained through undergraduate courses. To me this is a first, whereby at this level of studies I am privileged to solicit the basic mechanics of academic writing through Euclid University Coursepack ACA-401. EUCLID clearly stood out and

separated itself from the pack in academic delivery excellence as well as program tuition cost, it has by far the lowest tuition fees I have come across. To put into perspective, in my current degree program (Master of Global Project Management) that I am due for graduating this coming spring, the cost for a single course comparable to ACA-401 is \$2700 Australian Dollars. That said, I am truly proud and honored to be a part of this classy institution that is rich in building a strong foundation for its students and for the world beyond.

2) ESSAY WRITING

One of the biggest challenges students face is being able to organize pieces of information into a single meaningful document. At the helm of ACA-401 academic coursepack, is a guideline on academic essay writing. It highlights the stages student should take in structuring their work and writing an essay. What stood out for me is that, writing an essay is not a single-stage process; it is rather a process which involves several iterations. This being done to assist student in organizing their thoughts, understanding the essay topic, establishing structure and flow of ideas. In order for a student to conduct several iterations, there is a need to give yourself ample time between the start and deadline time. This is a critical component for gaining an in-depth understanding deliverable and the associated requirements to meet it.

Euclid University espoused the concept of early work starting in this ACA-401 course-pack. Key pointers in EUCLID's coursepack included being able to answer few early questions on the essay such as:

1. Information already known to you about the given topic, and it advises students to start working on the information you already know. Again, this notion of taping on information familiarity is key because it guides you on the direction you will need to take such as consulting others who could enlighten you, should you find yourself in an unfamiliar territory (EUCLID 2015, 2).
2. Through starting early, I am able to narrow down my focus area based on my understanding or lack of topic understanding on the given topic or question. Thus, it provides me with the ability to develop the premise for my argument. As such, early starting works as the central nervous system for the whole essay as it helps establish the direction and flow of information (EUCLID 2015, 5).

Another point raised in EUCLID's course is the importance of researching. My own understanding to researching is that, in order to deliver high quality paper, students need time to conduct a thorough research on the given topic. Without researching your work, it will lack the scientific backing it requires. Such scientific backing being knowledge and evidence which helps you in gaining a better understanding of the topic (EUCLID 2015, 2). Research enriches student's knowledge base and understanding of a question or topic; hence Euclid University saw it as an important factor to highlight. As a student, in many cases as I read papers and books, a system I had adopted was highlighting the key points that I find in each paper or book which relates to my study topic. I never really got into this idea which has been recommended to us in ACA-401 coursepack; taking down notes from

the readings. What I found however through following the method I was used to; I would end up flipping through the pages of the book looking for the ideas I highlighted earlier on as I was reading the chapter. What I found interesting however is that, on attempting to follow the guidelines provided which involves taking notes as I read, I could actually structure my notes in such a way that I would have the paper name where information was found, key pointers, page number, and have the source documented. This practice has cut-down time which I used to spend going through each book or article I read before, looking for the highlighted areas. This guided process takes the burden of looking through series or article to find a single page which was highlighted at the time I was reading the article, it then replaces that with the precision to point me directly where to find information and it is a great way to study and prepare for my essay writing.

3) STRUCTURE OF A PAPER

The AC-401 coursepack also introduced me to the required structure of the essay which is composed of the following:

1. Introduction,
2. Body, and
3. Conclusion.

The coursepack is informative in guiding me on what should be contained in my introduction. It gives insights on how ideas are framed within the essay and that the introduction should introduce the topic being researched on, so as work as a roadmap on how information is going to be organized within the document. Building from the argument constructed in the introduction, the essay creates a waterfall; feeding from the introduction is the body which is where evidence and research support is provided, looking at your views against those views shared by others. This is where I can support my argument through either authority referencing and or other academic sources which argues in favor or against my held opinion. Finally, the conclusion wraps all the key facts raised in the argument or thesis, providing a summary or all key facts. What ACA-401 Coursepack Period One also makes clear is that the conclusion does not carry any new information (EUCLID 2015, 4).

What we have here is a classic example of a structure of a paper, it gives the reader information related to what to expect as he/she looks at the report introduction. Having a structure ensures all students will be marked and graded against the same assessment rubric. However, when there is no prescribed paper/report structure, assessing students would be very difficult. In an organisational context such as BBC, CNN or other professional news reporting agencies; having the structure for reporting ensures news editors will qualify information in accordance with the established structure. As the paper is being edited, the editor is looking for information to be logically presented to readers in a sequential manner. That is, looking at whether the writer has put capital letters at the beginning of the sentence, whether cities are spelled according to the agreed spellings such as that established by the BBC news reporting.

A key reference point I explored during period one with reference to paper structure is that, without providing structure, there is room for creating and causing confusion. An example to this is one provided by the BBC News Style Guide as it provided the proper address for the Palestinian President: BBC highlighted that we start by the given name, followed by surname (New BBC Style Guide, 2013). This was evident on the Palestinian Leader: **Mahmoud Abbas**. What BBC news style guide has done is to take out the confusing whereby when you do not know which of the two given names represents the president's surname, you are clearly guided to what name represents the first name and what represents the surname (New BBC Style Guide, 2013). This is done to create uniformity in work delivery across all its news agents and its audience. In other words, there is a chance that if I did not know which name represent the president's surname; I could easily refer to him as President Mahmoud, which is a misrepresentation of his formal name identification, whereas his correct address should be President Abbas. It is just like addressing the U.S. President as President Donald, of which that is the first name not the surname, the correct address is President Trump or the full name starting with the given name, followed by the surname

4) REFERENCING

As I read period one coursepack, I came to a realization that every educational institution has its own preferred referencing style. Nonetheless, they all share some commonalities though the precise style may differ in its own right depending on the reference guide each institution uses. According to (EUCLID 2015, 5) coursepack, Euclid University; two methods are used whenever you are citing work, these are:

1. In-text citation, and
2. List of works cited

The guide provides information on where in-text citation is to be used in response and major papers, in this case; within the body of your text. It also provides information on where list of work cited is to appear. When it comes to citation requirements for Euclid University, to me serves as introductory to what Euclid University requires students to use. As a current student to Torrens University Australia and other past universities attended, and now, a student to Euclid University; I have not stopped studying since 2015. With such time of continuous studies, In-Text Citation and List of work cited has been the *key common feature* appearing to almost every university I enrolled and studied with. It is worth noting however that, in all past and current studies not including Euclid University; never was there a time I was required to reference using Turabian Reference Style. There was also never a time I was required to reference highlighting the version of English used. The reference styles I am familiar with are as follows:

1. Australian Guide to Legal Citation (AGLC) style
2. American Psychological Association (APA) style
3. Modern Language Association (MLA) style

With the enrollment to Euclid University, this has provided me with an opportunity to learn Turabian Reference style. While key elements appear the same, there are notable variances as you move from one style to another. Chicago -Turabian Style also provided me some insights on when *Italics* can be used by writers, such as; when emphasizing a new word in my text just as I did on the word italics above (EUCLID 2015, 4). Through reading the coursepack, I was able to learn about *Block Quotations*, and how *The Turabian Manual* advises us to treat them as we provide such quotations. Though the definition of longer quotation can be quite subjective, what is *not subjective* according to Turabian Manual is that when you have a quotation which runs for two or more sentences or covering about eight lines or even longer, the entirety of such reference paragraph would need to be indented and is to be provided as single-spaced (EUCLID 2015, 5). What has also become apparent is knowing when I am not required to cite and what stipulation is used to determine what is common knowledge and what constitutes it. In this case if I have used information in my assignment which is accessible on so many platforms such as that referenced in the lectures [smoking causes cancer] such information is available through hundreds if not thousands of bulletins. In such a case, that would be common information which requires not to cite. The idea being propounded by Euclid University is for students to have a clear understanding of the use of materials sourced and what needs to be credited to author and what does not.

5) DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AMERICAN & BRITISH ENGLISH

The content of ACA-401 coursepack enhanced my knowledge through gaining an understanding of the differences between American and British English word usage. Often times I used words such as “has” and “have” interchangeably, not realizing the mixing of different types of English being used in the same report (EUCLID 2015, 7). What the knowledge gained from EUCLID learning material has exposed me to is, I understand how some sentences could carry a logical meaning depending on the English context it is being used in. That is, I could write a statement that can be considered broken in British English and yet considered correct in American English.

Another point to note is that, I also had no knowledge of the punctuation format I was using as I used inverted commas in some instances and quotation marks at times, not realizing the two represented two different versions of English: American or British punctuation differences. On the other hand, I would use terms which are common to American English and those common to British English in the same essay. Being exposed to this information on differences has helped me broaden my understanding of the worldview.

6) CONCLUSION

Apply *RP Normal* style for body paragraphs at all levels. Go to the Zotero tab in conclusion, following the presets guidelines provided in lecture notes and reading resources, it is evident that careful consideration on paper delivery structure and mode must be observed. The context under which something is said is not always clear to the other person unless amplification of ideas to assist readers gain clarity on the context is done. As a student what has also become apparent is that authority citing plays a pivotal in substantiating my claims and when building a solid argument. Some of the things I never used to pay attention to were all made clear through accessing period one coursepack. It pays to find authority references related to the discussion or claim you are advancing, and this is achieved through conducting a research on the topic or related subject. As such, following guidelines provided by Euclid University will help me have a smooth study process as that ensures I remain on the right track and almost guarantees me a better outcome. What has been made clear also is, the construction of a document is critical to be followed and should not be ignored. Another point which became clear is that, a lack of proper referencing can be quite damaging to one's career and needs to be observed to avoid such pitfalls. Finally, there is more we can offer as students to ensure the attention of a reader is captured, otherwise we engage in self-destructive behavior as we lack to pay attention to things which enhances the quality of paper so as those which damages it.

REFERENCES

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